

DETERMINATION OF DUTY CYCLE IN THERMOSET PULTRUSION

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SUMMARY

Advantages of preheating the precursors to increase the line speed in thermoset pultrusion are studied and the work has been extended to quantify for the first time the duty cycle of a typical process and thereby provide an estimate of the Specific Energy Consumption (SEC). The results of the analysis were compared with experimental measurements made using a Fluke 345 Power Meter.

Key Words: Pultrusion, Thermal Analysis, Duty Cycle, Heating and curing cycle, Line Speed

Pultrusion is an important process for the manufacture of composites profiles based on thermosetting and thermoplastics resins. The process is essentially a heat transfer analysis problem as the heat is transferred from the die heaters to the precursors through the die, which in turn causes the resin fibre mixture to cure or set. In an earlier work by the authors it was shown that the line speed of the process can be increased from 0.35m/min to 0.85m/min by introducing a pre-heater in the process at 85°C.

The process parameters used in the simulation were taken from commercial Pultrusion line. The process begins with the reinforcement materials, which are held in creels or racks and fed continuously through a fibre guiding and resin impregnation system. Once formed to a shape, the impregnated reinforcement enters a heated curing die. This reinforcement is heated in the die through electrical heaters with PID controllers. The profile is cooled sufficiently as it travels to the haul off so that it is not deformed by the grippers. A saw is used to cut the profile to length before it is removed by the take off system.

In this study, a relationship is established between the initial temperature of precursors, the temperature of the die and rate of cure. Different input temperatures of the die are analyzed to check their effects on the line speed of the pultrusion. Heating and curing curves are plotted for the profile inside the die and then this simulation is extended for the duty cycle of the heaters.

Heat transfer equations are formulated to establish the temperature profiles and amount of heat transferred and solved by the Implicit Finite Difference Method. The Arrhenius equations and Kamal's Rate equations are used to calculate the degree of cure and are integrated by Fourth order Runge-Kutta Method for different iterations of the input parameters.

The analysis was performed on 6mm thick CFRP plate of width 35mm. The process was carried out in a 900mm long steel die equipped with a total of 600W heating elements.

RESULTS

Heating and curing curves are calculated for a wide number of line speeds and die entering temperatures. One such example is shown in the figure below for the mentioned parameters.

Line Speed m/min	Thickness mm	Charge Temp °C	Die Length mm
0.2~1	6	25	900

Figure 1. Temperature and Curing percentage of profiles along die length for mentioned parameters

EXPERIMENTS

It was not possible to verify these curves due to practical difficulties so it was decided to extend the same simulation to control algorithm of the power heaters. Hence the duty cycle of the heater is modeled and the resultant curves are verified by experimental measurements of the actual cycle using Fluke 345 power meter. The typical graph for a duty cycle of the profile is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Simulated Duty Cycle of the Heater